

Juvenile delinquency in Odisha (2003 to 2021): Understanding the trend and pattern of crime rate

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Abstract

Juvenile delinquency is an emerging social issue that has a deterrent effect on social law and order. It grabbed the attention of many educators, experts, and several law enforcement agencies. This research aims to explore juvenile delinquency in Odisha under different crime heads according to Indian Penal Code (IPC) and various percentage changes between the years 2003 to 2021. The basic motto of the present study is exploring the crimes committed by minors (Children in conflict with law). According to the statistical report by NCRB -The total cognizable crime rates are gradually spouting day by day. The crime rates for two decades of report showed that the significant changes have been reported from 2003 to 2021. The total number of cognizable crimes recorded in 2021 had increased more than 5 times in the past 2 decades. The NCRB report of 2016 showed the drastic increase of juvenile crime rates in different crime heads. Several crimes committed by the juveniles have been added in 2016 as delinquent activities that were not mentioned in the previous reports. A clear distinction is found in the data of the 2008 report and the 2016 report of the crimes committed by the juveniles. The rate and severity of major heinous crimes have also increased than it was before like the rate of conviction in the crime of murder has doubled within the year gap from 2008 to 2016, crime of rape has been six times increased, and kidnapping has increased 5 times more than before. Theft, Dacoity, robbery and burglary rates in Odisha went up in a progressive manner in recent years. The study will help to find out in analyzing the type of crimes and rate of crimes committed by the children in conflict with law in Odisha. This study will also help to promote several awareness or intervention programs at the individual level or government level.

Keywords: Juvenile delinquency, statistical data, Odisha

Introduction

The juvenile delinquent does not feel his disturbed personality. The intelligent man does not feel his intelligence or the introvert his introversion.” - B F Skinner.

Children are considered as most important assets of the country and a precious treasure for the future. Their proper development determines the future of the country. Securing the next generation is the greatest concern. The problem of juvenile delinquency (Children in Conflict with Law) is a complex social problem. The problems are more and more complicated and universal in all societies. Nowadays the magnitude of juvenile delinquency is increasing in a consistent manner. Juvenile delinquency is a topic of debate after 16th December 2012, Delhi gang rape and murder, commonly known as the Nirbhaya case in Delhi. The topic focused on the criminal responsibility of juveniles in India. Children are facing numerous social problems. Therefore, it demands to study of children and there is also a need to protect them. A healthy and educated child of today is the active and intelligent citizen of tomorrow. Effective development of children can only lead to a bright future for the country.

A juvenile or child means a minor person who has an age range below eighteen but in today's time, Juveniles are committing several adult-like heinous crimes such as rape, robbery, theft, and dacoits. For that matter considering them as minors is still a topic of debate. Young children don't have the maturity to understand the abnormal situation of life that reflects the immaturity in their thought process.

The Supreme Court expressed concern over rising rate of crimes in India involving juvenile accused, saying it needed immediate attention and that it was up to the government to revisit the benevolent juvenile justice law. (November 16th, 2022, Business Standard)

Odisha is a peace-loving state of India. But the cases of Children in Conflict with Law crimes are increasing day by day. After the analysis of leading newspapers reporting from Odisha, it is found that Odisha has witnessed an alarming rise in the rate of Juvenile delinquency over last 10 years.

Over 900 juveniles, mostly in the age of 13 to 18, were found involved in different crimes, including rape and murder in 2012. Those juveniles include 908 boys and 32 girls (Times of India, May 25, 2013). According to Times of India report (Times of India, Dec 2, 2017), NCRB data shows rise in crimes committed by children in Odisha. A total of 994 children were involved in different crimes (found in conflict with law) in 2016 as against 934 in the previous year. While bulk of the children were accused of committing theft and burglary, a number of them were allegedly involved in rape cases. According to the NCRB report, Odisha stood sixth in terms of registering 112 rape cases against minors after Madhya Pradesh (442), Maharashtra (258), Rajasthan (159), Chhattisgarh (148) and Uttar Pradesh (126). The Pioneer Newspaper (The Pioneer, 28 July 2017) in the article, "Children committing crime: Challenge grows tough for Odisha" reported that though Odisha is not a State with high incidence of children in conflict with law but the issue is growing. 37pc jump in juvenile crime NCRB revealed that there was a constant rise in the criminal cases registered against juveniles in the state over past few years. The data presented in the state assembly revealed that the case involving juveniles have witnessed a rise in 38 per cent over last five years (OrissaPost, August 13, 2019). Rise in involvement of minors in crimes in Ganjam district of Odisha are increasing. This came to light as names of over 102 children figured in various criminal cases over last three years. (OrissaPost, April 15, 2021). The New Indian Express (13th October, 2019) reported that juvenile crime is a headache for Odisha's Ganjam police where 89 minors arrested by Berhampur police for committing various crimes between 2016 and 2019. Argus news (Nov 11, 2021) reported in the article "Rise of violent youngsters in Odisha, a dangerous trend" that members of the violent gangs like notorious Koi Bhai Nahin (KBN) gang of Bhubaneswar, Sandha Group of Cuttack etc. are youngsters, mostly teenagers. This is a cause of concern for police as well as peaceful Odia society as a whole.

The analysis of the statistical data of the Children in Conflict with Law of Odisha will give a clear understanding of the situation. So, this study is aimed to study juvenile delinquency of Odisha under different crime heads and the growth rates throughout the successive years from 2003 to 2021.

Objectives of the Study

The present study has been conducted with the following objective:

To explore juvenile delinquency in Odisha (IPC) under different crime heads and various percentage changes between the years 2003 to 2021.

Data Base and Research Methodology

The major source of the data is secondary in nature. The data set has been collected from the National Crime Records Bureau Year book(2003- 2021) under Ministry of Home affairs. Cases have been counted from 2003 to 2021 to find out the increase/ decrease in each type of crime broadly categorized under Juvenile delinquency (Children in Conflict with Law).

Study area: Odisha

Table1: Various types of crimes under Juvenile Delinquency cases of Odisha over the study period 2003-2021

Juveniles apprehended under different IPC crimes	Murder (Sec 302, 303 IPC)	Attempt To Commit Murder (Sec 307 IPC)	C.H. Not Amounting To Murder (Sec 304, 308 IPC)	Rape (Sec 376 IPC)	Kidnapping & Abduction (Sec 363 - 369, 371 - 373 IPC)	Dacoity (Sec 395-398 IPC)	Preparation & Assembly For Dacoity (Sec 399 - 402 IPC)	Robbery Sec 392-394, 397, 398 IPC)
2003	8	3	0	12	2	5	0	0
2004	12	2	0	17	1	3	0	1
2005	20	12	0	16	4	2	0	2
2006	15	14	0	19	0	5	0	6
2007	28	18	1	32	6	2	1	10
2008	16	13	0	24	7	2	1	18
2009	14	14	0	27	4	10	0	16
2010	18	10	0	16	7	3	5	24
2011	19	7	0	44	13	8	0	17
2012	40	19	1	70	14	10	2	32
2013	32	26	0	91	15	12	1	24
2014	19	27	0	79	49	22	4	39
2015	29	35	7	105	27	9	2	49
2016	34	31	2	122	37	16	0	52
2017	21	13	0	54	3	12	2	63
2018	9	10	0	60	6	6	0	19
2019	3	53	0	24	9	4	0	1
2020	10	16	0	34	9	7	0	1
2021	9	20	0	34	9	13	0	20

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs

The statistical representation is describing the criminal activity conducted by the juvenile delinquents(Children in Conflict with Law) from the year 2003 to 2021 under different crime heads.

A quick reflection of the NCRB data from 2003 to 2021

Figure-1 Murder rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-1 represents the analysis of murder rates of juvenile delinquency in Odisha (IPC) juvenile (people under the age 18) covering the period from 2003 to 2021. The murder rates among juveniles are in peak in the year 2012. The juvenile murder rate fell in between the year 2018 to 2020. The lowest rate of murder committed by juvenile delinquency is in the year 2019.

Figure-2 Attempt to Commit murder rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-2 represents the number of attempts to commit murder hiked in the year 2019. The number of attempts to commit murder was lowest more than two decades ago in the year 2003 and 2004.

Figure-3 Murder, Attempt to Commit murder and C.H. not amounting to murder rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-3 is the graphical representation of the major heinous crimes such as Murder, Attempt to commit murder, Culpable Homicide not amounting to murder. The all 3 types of murder rates in the year 2015 and 2016 is on high.

Figure-4 Rape rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-4 is the graphical representation of the number of cases of rape cases through the respective years from 2003 to 2021. In 2016 the rate of rape cases rate is maximum than other respective years. In the year 2021 the murder rate is 34 in 2021 which is 3 times more than reported crime in 2003.

Figure-5 Kidnapping and abduction rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Kidnapping and abduction rate is highest in 2014 i.e. 49 and 2nd highest in 2016 and the number is 37. The rate is lowest in 2004. A little drop in kidnapping after 2017

But still the number is 9.

Figure-6 Dacoity rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

The Figure-6 showed that the rate of dacoity had a significant rise from 2013 to 2017. After a small dip for 2 yrs. Again in 2020 and 2021 the number of dacoity cases have also increased.

Figure-7 Preparation and assembly for Dacoity rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

The preparation and assembly for dacoity rates are seen in the year 2006 and 2008. The dacoity rate is highest in the year 2010 i.e. 5 and in 2014 it is 4 the rate is increasing intermittently.

Figure-8 Dacoity and Preparation and assembly for Dacoity rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-8 represents the rate of dacoity and preparation and assembly for dacoity to become changing remarkably step by step manner from 2013 to 17 the rate is high after 3yrs. Both dacoity and preparation for assembly for dacoity is significantly reaching its peak in a progressive manner.

Figure-9 Robbery rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

The rate of robbery has successively increased till 2017 but rate has declined after that year. As per the report 2021 the Robbery rate has significantly improved than its previous year report.

Table-2: Various types of crimes under Juvenile Delinquency cases of Odisha over the study period 2003-2021

Juveniles apprehended under different IPC crimes	Burglary (Sec 449-452, 454, 455, 457 - 460 IPC)	Theft (Sec 379-382 IPC)	Riots (Sec 143-145, 147-151, 153, 153A, 153B, 157, 158, 160 IPC)	Criminal Breach Of Trust (Sec 406 -409 IPC)	Cheating (Sec 419, 420 IPC)	Counterfeiting (Sec 231- 254, 489A – 489D IPC)	Arson (Sec 435, 436, 438 IPC)	Hurt (Sec 323- 333, 335- 338 IPC)
2003	38	78	9	0	1	0	1	10
2004	53	92	4	0	3	0	1	8
2005	64	117	12	0	1	0	4	25
2006	68	152	15	0	2	0	1	16
2007	89	198	29	0	0	1	3	50
2008	79	161	14	0	1	0	1	29
2009	40	117	12	0	1	1	0	18
2010	46	97	13	6	1	0	1	45
2011	73	106	6	0	1	0	1	45
2012	73	136	28	0	6	0	3	67
2013	78	234	27	1	0	0	4	84
2014	120	205	13	0	3	1	2	12
2015	113	151	17	0	0	0	0	16
2016	133	171	0	0	1	0	1	36
2017	223	568	12	0	0	0	0	9
2018	41	795	10	0	0	0	0	11
2019	136	910	0	0	2	0	1	1
2020	77	592	3	0	1	0	0	10
2021	83	407	8	0	0	0	0	8

Source: National Crime Records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs

Figure-10 Burglary rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-10 shows the rate of burglary is on hike in the year 2017 that means the number is 233 and the second and third highest rate in the year 2019 and 2016 and the numbers are 136 and 133 respectively. A remarkable variation is found in between the first and second decade report.

Figure-11 Theft rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-11 represents the theft rates in Odisha is showing a spectacular difference in recent years than previous years. The rapid increase in the rates of theft in between the years 2018 to 2020 The rate of theft is highest in the year 2019. The recent 5 years showed a significant variation than previous years

Figure-12 Riots rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-12 implies the riots rates is gradually declining in recent years than previous years. The riots rate is highest in the year 2007.

Figure-13 Cheating rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-13 reflects that 2012 is the peak period for cheating rates among juveniles in Odisha. The cheating rate varies recurrently from year to year.

Figure-14 Arson rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-14 focused on the details of arson in a multimodal manner. 2005 and 2013 highest amount of juvenile delinquent activity for arson was committed.

Figure-15 Hurt rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-15 describes the rate of hurt is on its peak in 2013 and the recorded number is 84, which catch the attention to draw into this matter.

Table-3: Various types of crimes under Juvenile Delinquency cases of Odisha over the study period 2003-2021

Juveniles apprehended under different IPC crimes	Dowry Deaths (Sec 304B IPC)	Molestation (Sec 354 IPC)	Sexual Harassment (Sec 509 IPC)	Cruelty by Husband and Relatives (Sec 498A IPC)	Importation Of Girls (Sec 366B IPC)	Causing Death By Negligence (Sec 304A IPC)	Other IPC Crimes	Total Cog. Crimes Under IPC
2003	0	4	1	0	0	0	47	219
2004	1	5	0	0	0	0	53	256
2005	0	25	3	4	0	0	72	389
2006	3	11	1	4	0	0	59	394
2007	2	14	0	7	0	0	136	627
2008	0	9	4	1	0	3	94	477
2009	0	4	2	1	0	1	99	381
2010	1	7	0	0	0	4	99	403
2011	2	9	0	2	0	2	100	455
2012	0	15	0	3	0	7	113	639
2013	0	34	2	5	0	4	229	903
2014	0	37	5	3	0	5	164	813
2015	0	39	7	0	0	0	294	910
2016	0	0	0	16	0	7	241	977
2017	0	12	0	1	0	0	72	1106
2018	0	0	0	0	0	2	28	1069
2019	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1158
2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	1071
2021	0	0	0	4	0	2	8	1321

Figure-16 Sexual Harassment and Molestation rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-16 depicts that the rate of molestation is highest in the year 2015. The incidents of crime reported in Odisha are reported in a harmonical manner and no cases in the recent years have been recorded. No sexual harassment cases have been recorded from 2016 to 2021. But it is observed that the amount of crime reported within every bit of pause.

Figure-17 Cruelty by Husband and Relatives rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-17 the rate of increase of cruelty by husband and relatives is at peak in the year 2016.

Figure-18 Causing death by Negligence rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

As per the Figure-18, no case of causing death by negligence has been reported from 2003 to 2007 but from onwards 2008 is a matter of concern. In 2012 and 2016 the reported crime by juveniles are highest rate i.e. 7.

Figure-19 Other IPC Crimes rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-19 the other IPC crimes is increasing in a progressive manner. The upmost elevated rate is measured in the year 2016. In 2021 the rate is fell down dramatically than previous reports.

Figure-20 Total Cognizable Crimes under IPC rate of juveniles in Odisha from 2003-2021

Figure-20 reflects the rate of total cognizable crime by juvenile delinquent under Indian Penal code (IPC) has been increasing day by day. The accelerating rate of total juvenile crimes are seen throughout the 2 decades. Several new crimes have been added and several crimes are replaced and renamed. The rising rate of juvenile delinquency need an immediate attention to overcome the concerned issue.

Conclusions

The offending rate of delinquent activity by juveniles is gradually accelerating and these had an increasing effect over time. Several conclusions we get from the graphical representation of the data are

- The total cognizable crime rates are gradually increasing day by day. The rate of crime in 2021 has been increased 5 to 6 times than the crime was recorded in 2003.
- In the year 2021 report as compared to the 2003 statistical report implies a clear representation of the amount of drastic increase in the different heads of juvenile crime rates.
- Not only the rate of increase is a growing concern, as well as the addition of several delinquencies throughout the year, is an emerging issue too.
- As well as several delinquency rates are also declining for example rate of dowry deaths, arson, counterfeiting and criminal breach of trust etc. related to juveniles has decreased within the last 10 years.
- Several heinous crimes like- murder have doubled up within the year gap from 2008 to 2016, rape has been six times increased than it was before, and kidnapping has increased 5 times more than before.
- Comparatively, the conviction rate under IPC under theft, burglary, is notably increased.
- The graphs (causing death by negligence, cruelty by husband and relatives, sexual harassment, arson etc.) are patterned like a forecasting chart, that makes a trending line of the past intermittent effect which predicts that the occurrences of the crimes in the future

The statistics show that in recent years crime rates are on a hike. This demands a situation to think about the most important creation of the world i.e. the children and help them to provide opportunity not to

develop unhealthy attitudes and behavior and create a foundation to prevent juvenile delinquent activities and recidivism.

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